

EFFECT OF MICROSTRUCTURE ON THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF CARBON (C) FIBERS AND C-C COMPOSITES

Suraj Rawal, Neil Murdie*, and Mohan Misra
Martin Marietta Astronautics Group, Denver, CO 80201

* Materials Technology Center, Southern Illinois University at Carbondale,
Carbondale, IL 62901

ABSTRACT

Thermal conductivity of graphite fibers is strongly governed by the phonon conduction process, the longer the mean free path, the higher the thermal conductivity. In this investigation, a relationship has been developed between the microstructural parameters and phonon mean free path, and associated thermal conductivity of as received (AR) and heat treated pitch fibers.

X-ray diffraction patterns of three different pitch fibers P95 WG, P100 and P120 were examined to determine the crystalline parameters, and to calculate the thermal conductivity. The crystalline parameters included crystallite length, L_a , crystallite stack height, L_c , void content, full width at half maximum ($Z_{(00,2)}$) and degree of graphitization. Also, P95 WG fiber was heat treated (i.e., P95 WG-HT) to determine the changes in crystalline parameters and thermal conductivity. The thermal conductivity values calculated from the microstructural parameters exhibit strong correlation with the measured conductivity values.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Pitch (P) derived carbon fibers (e.g., AMOCO's P100, P120 or K1100) exhibit thermal conductivity ranging from 520 to 1100/W/m-K, and the potential exists to produce fibers with significantly higher conductivity. These high thermal conductivity (k) carbon fibers are being investigated to produce carbon-carbon (C-C) composites for thermal management applications. In addition, low cost, low modulus (low k) pitch precursor fibers are often graphitized by heat treatment (at 2200°C) to obtain higher modulus and conductivity in C-C composites. For example, specific grades of P25 and P55 fibers have been heat treated to obtain elastic modulus of 95 msi and 105 msi respectively. During heat treatment, microstructural changes occurring within the fibers influence their modulus, strength and conductivity [1-6]. This paper examines the relationship between the microstructure and thermal conductivity of carbon fiber and C-C composite.

Measured microstructural parameters such as crystallite length, degree of crystallite orientation and void content were used to estimate the phonon-mean free path values for different fibers. The pitch fibers with a high degree of graphitization had longer mean free paths and exhibited strong correlation with the measured conductivity values. Specific details of the proposed relationship between the microstructural parameters and thermal conductivity of carbon fibers are discussed below.

2.0 MATERIALS

Pitch based carbon fibers and carbon-carbon (C-C) composites were used in this investigation. Amoco's pitch based fibers included: 1) P95 WG-Precursor**: As received fibers; 2) P95 WG-Heat Treated (HT); 3) P100; and 4) P120.

** Specific grade of P25 that can be heat treated (at 2200°C) to obtain elastic modulus of 95 msi, referred to as P95 WG.

The carbon fibers were used in producing P95 WG-HT/T300, P100/T300 and P120/T300 6:1 unidirectional fabrics. From these fabrics carbon-phenolic prepegs and subsequently flat C-C panels were produced by B.F. Goodrich Supertemp, Santa Fe Springs, CA, using their proprietary chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) process.

3.0 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

The microstructure of C-C composites were examined using a Hitachi 500 TEM. The fibers, the intrabundle matrix, and the interbundle matrix were examined by selected area diffraction (SAD). The SAD patterns of the specific areas were obtained using the 50 μm intermediate aperture to give a selected area of $< 1 \mu\text{m}$.

- Interplanar Spacing, $d_{(00,2)}$

$$d_{(hkl)} = \lambda / (2 \sin \theta)$$

$$\lambda = \text{x-ray wavelength}$$

$$\theta = \text{scattering or Bragg Angle}$$

- Degree of Graphitization (g_p)

$$g_p = (0.344 - d_{(00,2)}) / (0.344 - 0.3354)$$

$$0.344 \text{ nm} = d_{(hkl)} \text{ Turbostratic Carbon}$$

$$0.3354 \text{ nm} = d_{(hkl)} \text{ Graphite}$$

- Void Content, ($\% V_v$)

$$\% V_v = \left[1 - \frac{(\rho d_{(hkl)})_{\text{Fiber}}}{(\rho d_{(hkl)})_{\text{Graphite}}} \right] \times 100$$

$$\rho_{\text{Graphite}} = 2.26 \text{ g/cm}^3$$

- Crystallite Stack Height, L_c

$$L_c = [\lambda] / [\beta_{(00,2)}(2\theta) \cos \theta]$$

$$\beta_{(00,2)}(2\theta) - \text{Integral breadth in } 2\theta \text{ radians}$$

- Crystallite Length, L_a

$$L_a = 1.84 \lambda / B\left(\frac{1}{2}, 2\theta\right) \cos \theta$$

$$B\left(\frac{1}{2}, 2\theta\right) = \text{Measured Full-Width at Half-Maximum (FWHM) of the Asymmetric Profile}$$

- $Z_{(00,2)}$ = Full-width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the azimuthal scans of (00,2) reflections.

3.2 Thermal Conductivity Measurements

Inplane thermal conductivity of composite specimens was measured by the flash diffusivity method at Thermophysical Properties Research Laboratory, Purdue Univ., Indiana. In the flash diffusivity method, the front face of a disc-shaped specimen is subjected to a short burst of radiant energy while the temperature of the rear surface is measured. The thermal diffusivity is computed from the temperature rise versus time data, and the thermal conductivity is calculated as the product of the thermal diffusivity, the specific heat, and the density.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Microstructure Of C-C Composite

Figure 1 shows the bright field TEM image of the interface structure between the resin region (A) and the CVI carbon region (B). In the region A, the structure of resin char is isotropic, being composed of small randomly oriented crystallites. The CVI carbon consists of two layers, where the first layer (C) is about 0.5 μm wide and also consists of randomly oriented crystallites. Average crystallite size in the CVI carbon is larger than those in the resin. The second layer of CVI carbon (D) is 1-2 μm wide, strongly oriented and consisting of much larger crystallites with many lenticular shaped microcracks between the individual crystallites. The SAD patterns of resin char indicated a non-graphite structure with random orientation of crystallites, whereas the (002) arcs in the SAD pattern of the CVI carbon layer, indicated the anisotropic structure.

Figure 1 TEM Bright Field Image of Interface Between Resin and CVI Matrix in P100/T300 C-C composite (A: Resin, B: CVI Carbon Consisting of 1st Layer (C) and 2nd Layer (D))

Various TEM micrographs of the C-C composites indicated that the microstructural characteristics of the fiber, matrix and interface regions were representative of a typical CVI processed C-C. The mechanical property tests indicated good correlation between the measured and predicted properties suggesting adequate bond at the fiber matrix interface. With good interfacial bond, the thermal conductivity of fibers should mostly contribute to the thermal conductivity of the composite, because non-graphitic carbon matrix has inherently low conductivity.

4.2 Thermal Conductivity Of Composites

Table 1 lists the measured thermal conductivity of each C-C composite. For example, P100/C exhibits an axial thermal conductivity of 222 W/m-K as compared to 150.4 W/m-K for P95 WG-HT/C composite. Each composite has low thermal conductivity (4 - 9 W/m-K) in the fill and through thickness directions suggesting that the thermal conductivity of the CVI matrix, and transverse thermal conductivity of each carbon fiber are very low. Table 1 also lists the calculated axial thermal conductivity (K_f^a) of each fiber (using the thermal conductivity rule of mixture for the conductivity of C-C) and compares it with the typical thermal conductivity values, as listed by Amoco [7].

Calculated values of P100 and P120 fibers are 88% and 93% respectively of the thermal conductivity values reported by Amoco [7]. These differences can be attributed either to the defect/void volume of the consolidated composite or to the reasonable scatter (e.g., 600 - 640 W/m-K for P120 fiber) in the reported conductivities of each carbon fiber.

Table 1 Thermal Conductivity Values of C-C Composites and Pitch Fibers

C-C Composite (6:1 Unifabric)	Fiber Volume	Thermal Conductivity (W/m-K)			Fiber Thermal Conductivity (W/m-K)	
		Warp	Fill	Through Thickness	Calculated*	Typical
P95 WG/T300	----	----	----	----	----	22
P95 WG-HT-T300	50	150.4	9.6	3.4	305	345
P100/T300	50	222	7.7	3.4	450	520
P120/T300	50	290	9.6	3.4	590	640

* Based on rule of mixture for thermal conductivity of C-C, assuming nearly zero conductivity for CVI matrix

4.3 Microstructure Of Pitch-Based Carbon Fibers

Figure 3 shows the dark field TEM image of the P95 WG-HT fiber, indicating the presence of several individual fibrils oriented parallel to the fiber axis. The fibrils appear as bright and dark bands and are linear in shape. Each fibril consists of a number of crystallites with similar basal plane orientation. A typical fibril is a few microns in length and 50-100Å in thickness. The SAD patterns of P95 WG-HT, P100 and P120 fibers exhibited a high degree of crystallinity. The fibrils, within the P100 and P120 fibers, appeared to be wider (100 - 200Å), than the fibrils of P95 WG-HT fiber.

Figure 3 Dark Field Image of Pitch Fiber Showing Individual Fibrils

4.4 X-RAY DIFFRACTION OF PITCH FIBERS

Table 2 lists the results of the x-ray diffraction studies on the four fibers P95 WG, P95 WG-HT, P100 and P120. These results indicate that the as-received P95 WG fiber is the least graphitic fiber with a $d_{(00,2)}$ spacing of 3.46Å. Also, it exhibits the lowest crystallite length; L_a being 40Å. After heat treatment (at 2200°C) of the same fiber (i.e., P95 WG-HT), the $d_{(00,2)}$ decreased to 3.39Å and the average L_a increased to 373Å.

The P100 fiber was graphitic in structure with a $d_{(00,2)}$ spacing of 3.38Å, and larger L_a (\approx 561Å) values compared to the P95 WG-HT fiber. Graphite character of the P120 fiber was evident with the $d_{(00,2)}$ basal plane spacing of 3.37Å and average L_a value of 698Å.

Table 2 X-Ray Diffraction Results of Different Pitch Fibers

Fiber	ρ gm/cc	$d_{(00,2)}$ (Å)	L_c (Å)	L_a (Å)	g_p (%)	V_v (%)	FWHM or $Z_{(00,2)}$ (°)
P95 WG	1.90	3.46	73	40	0.02	13.78	31.9
P95 WG-HT	2.10	3.39	196	373	58	6.17	8
P100	2.15	3.38	276	561	69.8	4.12	5.6
P120	2.18	3.37	286	698	81.0	3.0	5.6

Based on measured $d_{(00,2)}$ spacings, and fiber densities, values of degree of graphitization, g_p and void content of each fiber were calculated and included in Table 2. The calculated g_p values indicate that the degree of graphitization in the pitch fibers increased as follows: P120 > P100 > P95 WG-HT > P95 WG; consistent with the TEM images of these fibers.

Figure 4(a) shows a schematic of a carbon fiber indicating crystallite orientation, crystallite stack height and crystallite length. The azimuthal scans (Fig. 4b) of intensity versus chi (χ) angle for P95 WG and P95 WG-HT fibers indicate that the FWHM or $Z_{(00,2)}$ values decrease with increasing graphite structure from P95 WG to P95 WG-HT fiber.

Figure 4 Crystallite orientation (FW-HM or $Z_{(00,2)}$) for P95 WG and P195 WG-HT Fibers (a) Schematic of Carbon Fiber, (b) Azimuthal Scan of Intensity Versus X Angle

4.5 Relationship Between Microstructural Parameters And Fiber Thermal Conductivity

Solids transmit thermal energy by two modes: (i) phonon conduction, and (ii) electronic conduction, either one of which or both may operate. Phonon conduction occurs in all solids, as energy may be transferred by means of elastic vibrations of the lattice moving through the crystal in the form of waves. In metals, however free electrons moving through the lattice also carry energy in a manner similar to thermal conduction by a gas phase.

If the forces between atoms were perfectly harmonic, then the thermal conduction due to phonon-phonon (normal type) interaction would be extremely easy, and the only limit to the mean free

path (Λ_{ph}) would be the dimensions of the material. But the forces between atoms are mostly anharmonic, and there exists another type of phonon-phonon interaction, known as an Umklapp process where the total energy is conserved while the phonon momentum is not. Due to these Umklapp collisions, which are important over a wide temperature range, the mean free path of phonons is short. Also, various lattice imperfections, such as dislocations, crystal boundaries, impurities, and porosities give rise to anharmonicities and result in phonon scattering, which further decreases the mean free path and affects the conductivity.

Thermal conductivity of graphite due to phonon conduction is given by the following expression:

$$k \approx \rho C_v (T) v \Lambda_{ph} \quad [1]$$

where: ρ = density
 $C_v(T)$ = Specific heat/unit volume at temperature T
 v = velocity

Average phonon velocity depends on the lattice vibration spectrum and phonon interaction mechanisms. Phonon mean free path is influenced by microstructural parameters such as L_c , L_a , $Z_{(00,2)}$ and void content. The effective Λ_{ph} along the axis of the fiber (at a specific temperature) influences the axial thermal conductivity of the pitch fiber. It appears that if random crystallites are long and exhibit a high degree of alignment (i.e., low $Z_{(00,2)}$) parallel to the fiber axis then Λ_{ph} should be long.

i.e.: $\Lambda_{ph} \propto L_a$, and [2]

$\Lambda_{ph} \propto \cos(1/2 Z_{(00,2)})$ [3]

Effective mean free path could also be long if the void content of the fiber and consequently the phonon scattering is low, i.e.:

$\Lambda_{ph} \propto (1-V_v)$ [4]

Combining the proportionality relationships (i.e., Eqns. 2, 3, and 4) yields the following expression:

$\Lambda_{ph} \propto L_a \cdot \cos(1/2 Z_{(00,2)}) \cdot (1-V_v)$ [5]

i.e.: $k \approx \rho C_v (T) v [L_a \cdot \cos(1/2 Z_{(00,2)}) \cdot (1-V_v)]$ [6]

With the increased degree of graphitization in the pitch based graphite fibers (Table 2) crystalline parameters L_c and L_a increase, and $Z_{(00,2)}$ and V_v decrease.

For the pitch derived carbon fibers, the phonon mean free path was calculated both from the crystalline parameters (i.e., Eqn. 6) and also from typical fiber thermal conductivity values (i.e., Eqn. 1). Based on these calculations, the Λ_{ph} value of 31.5Å for P95 WG fiber increased to 349Å for P95 WG-HT, providing a measure of enhanced conductivity. Figure 5 shows a plot of the axial thermal conductivity versus phonon mean free path of different pitch fibers indicating a linear relationship described in Equation 6. Also, Figure 6 shows that the calculated thermal conductivities (from Eqn. 6) are reasonably consistent with the typical conductivities of carbon fibers. The correlation between thermal conductivity and Λ_{ph} suggests that crystallite dimension, crystallite misorientation and void content are the key microstructural parameters influencing the phonon mean free path in carbon fibers

Figure 5 Axial thermal Conductivity Versus Calculated Phonon Mean Free Path of the Pitch Fibers

5.0 CONCLUDING REMARKS

X-ray diffraction patterns of three different pitch fibers, P95 WG, P100 and P120, were examined to determine the crystalline parameters, and their relationship with thermal conductivity. The crystalline parameters included crystallite dimension, L_a ; crystallite size, L_c ; void content, full width at half maximum ($Z_{(00,2)}$) and degree of graphitization. In particular, P95 WG fiber was heat treated (i.e., P95 WG-HT) and changes in crystalline parameters were examined to determine the extent of graphitization.

Thermal conductivity of graphite fibers is primarily influenced by the phonon conduction process; the longer the mean free path, the higher the thermal conductivity. In this investigation, a relationship was developed between phonon mean free path and crystalline parameters: $\Delta\phi$ being the product of L_a , $\cos(1/2 Z_{(00,2)})$ and $(1-V_v)$. Therefore, if a low modulus, low conductivity pitch fiber could be heat treated to attain a high degree of graphitization, then it should exhibit high L_a , low $Z_{(00,2)}$ and low V_v . From the crystalline parameters, the calculated thermal conductivities were nearly equivalent with the typical thermal conductivity values of the pitch fibers.

Figure 6 Calculated Axial thermal Conductivity Versus Typical Thermal Conductivity of the Pitch Fibers

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by Martin Marietta Independent Research and Development Project D-81R, Materials Technology.

REFERENCES

1. D.P. Anderson, "Carbon Fiber Morphology: Wide Angle X-Ray Studies of Pitch- and PAN-Based Carbon Fibers," WRDC-TE-89-4072, US Air Force Technical Report, July 1989.
2. D.P. Anderson, "Carbon Fiber Morphology, II: Expanded Wide-Angle X-Ray Diffraction Studies of Carbon Fibers," WRDC-TR-90-4137, US Air Force Technical Report, February 1991.
3. A.S. Castro and D.P. Anderson, "Correlation of Structure and Compressive Strength in Pitch-Based Graphite Fibers," Proc. of the Am. Soc. for Composites, 5th Tech. Conf. on Composite Materials, pp. (1990).
4. K. Bran, and W. M. Phillips, "Effect of Heat Treatment on Carbon Fibers," SAMPE Journal, Vol. 26, No. 5, September/October 1990.
5. Dr. Peter Pollock, University of Dayton Reserach Institute, Private Communication, 17 June 1992.
6. Brian Sullivan, MSNW, Private communication, 28 September 1992.
- 7 Amoco Performance Products, Thornel, and Pitch Fiber Data , 1992